

Nanosized Cs-Pollucite Zeolite Synthesized Under Mild Condition And Its Catalytic Behavior

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Abstract:

Nanoscale cesium-pollucite zeolite (ANA topology) free of organic template is synthesized free of organic template. The crystallization is taken place at mild temperature and pressure (180 °C, 22 bar) compared to previous works. Powder XRD analysis reveals that the nanocrystals can be crystallized from a clear precursor solution of 16.5SiO₂:1Al₂O₃:5.3Cs₂O:175H₂O within 50 h. The resulting nanocrystals exhibit trapezohedron shape and has a Si/Al ratio of 4.11. The nanocrystals possess a mean particle size of 79.4 nm and they are colloiddally stable in water. In addition, Perkin condensation of benzaldehyde with acetic anhydride catalyzed by nanosized Cs-pollucite zeolite under non-microwave instant heating condition is also demonstrated and discussed.

Keywords:

Nanocrystals; Cesium-pollucite; Template-free synthesis; Mild synthesis condition; Perkin Condensation

Research Area:

Physical Chemistry

Multifunctional Role Of Nanoemulsion In The Improvement Of Oral And Brain Penetration Of Therapeutics

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Abstract:

Nanoemulsions are thermodynamically stable colloidal dispersion of oil phase in the aqueous environment within the nanometric size range, where the dispersed phase is stabilized by the presence of thin film of surface-active agents. Application of this nanocarrier in delivering therapeutics is immense, where poorly soluble drugs are incorporated into the lipid core to promote permeation through different biological barriers. Enteral administration of this formulation improve bioavailability of lipophilic drugs to provide enhanced efficacy and safety superior to that of conventional formulations of equivalent doses of the same therapeutic. Further, administration of this formulation also found to enhance penetration of drugs to the central nervous system, may be through intranasal administration. Therefore, this platform has the potential to circumvent rigid blood-brain-barrier to make the drug available to the brain. Consequently, this multifunctional nanocarrier results in improved permeability, cell and tissue targeting for improved therapeutic function. Thus, choice of suitable oils and surfactants in the presence of surface modifiers can serve to safe and effectively deliver the therapeutics across oral and/or brain barriers.

Keywords:

Nanoemulsion; enhance penetration; biological barrier; lipophilic agents; improved bioavailability

Experimental studies on high-quality synthetic wood production using industrial waste and mixed waste catalyst

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Abstract:

Throughout different areas of environmental sustainability, such as disaster risk reduction and management, decision and policy making; solid waste management is indeed a thematic matter in an important field of current interest. A typical solid waste management system displays an array of problems, these public health, environmental, and management issues are caused by various factors which constrain the development of effective solid waste management systems. If the lack of knowledge, experience and the awareness of the need for a change in waste management is inversely slow. However, the circular economy, which has suddenly been put under the spotlight, aims to redefine growth, focusing on positive society-wide benefits. The aim of this paper is to show the development of a matrix to explain three categories of waste which result from the failure of users to properly use a resource. These categories were illustrated by examples built on practical industrial waste measurements, as a development process. Different facets of waste from an activity perspective were categorized; so they can contribute to improved waste management practices. It is shown an application of the industrial solid waste (polypropylene waste, peels of rice and zinc stearate) and an assessment of what could be the sustainable wood of the future.

Keywords:

Waste Management. Wasteful of Civil Constructions. SocioEnvironmental Context, Business perspective

Studies on the Effective Removal Efficiency by Peanut Hulls (Red and White) Supported Magnetically

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Abstract:

Magnetically responsive composite materials, prepared by medication of diamagnetic materials by magnetic fluids (ferrofluids) have already found many important applications in various areas of biosciences, medicine, biotechnology, environmental technology etc. The present work is concerned with the raw peanut hull (RPH) and magnetically peanut hull (MPH) as a biosorbent for waste water treatment. Characterizations of biosorbent were carried out by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT IR), X-Ray Fluorescence (EDXRF) and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). FT-IR images showed the presence of hydroxyl, carbonyl and carboxyl groups which can involve in the biosorption process. The major elements of samples were analyzed by using X-Ray Fluorescence. The surface features and morphological characteristics of RPH and MPH by SEM. Raw peanut hulls (RPH), Ferro fluid and Prepared magnetic peanut hulls (MPH) were used for the investigation of colour removal efficiency, heavy metal removal efficiency by using model solution and turbidity removal efficiency was also carried out from beer factory, tap water (laboratory), and pun haling river water.

Keywords:

Magnetic peanut hulls, methylene blue, colour removal efficiency, turbidity, ferrofluid,

Raw Peanut Hull(RPH)

Ferro Fluid

Magnetic Peanut Hull

References:

- [1] N.A. Taha, and A.E. Maghraby : “Characterization of Peanut Hulls and Adsorption Study on Basic Dye: Isotherm and Kinetic Analysis”. International journal of innovative research in technology & science, 2(2), 9-18, 2014.
- [2] C. Namasivayam, N. Muniasamy, K. Gayatri, M. Rani. and K. Ranganathan : “Removal of Dyes from Aqueous Solutions by Cellulosic Waste Orange Peel”. Bioresour. Technol., 57, 37–43, 1996.
- [3] C. Namasivayam, and N. Kanchana. “Waste banana pith as adsorbent for color removal from wastewaters”. Chemosphere, 25, 1691–1706, 1992.
- [4] L. H., Wang and C. I. Lin: “Adsorption of Lead (II) Ion from Aqueous Solution Using Rice Hull Ash”. Ind. Eng. Chem. Res., 47, 4891-4897, 2008.
- [5] D. Hritcu, M. I. Popa, N. Popa, V. Badescu, and V. Balan : Preparation and characterization of magnetic chitosan nanospheres, Turk.J.Chem., Vol.33, pp.785–796, 2009

Exploring Target-Ligand Binding Selectivity of Hybrid Molecular Scaffolds by Virtual Screening: Identifying Pathways to Find “Hits” as Potential 5-Lipoxygenase Inhibitors

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Abstract:

5-Lipoxygenase (5-LO) is a rate-limiting en-zyme which catalyses the conversion of ara-chidonic acid to leukotriene B4 (LTB4). LTB4, an inflammatory mediator, triggers atherosclerosis. The selective inhibitors of 5-LO to block atherosclerosis is currently unavailable. Modern drug discoveries show that hybrid molecules can provide combination therapies in a single multi-functional agent, leads to novel hybrid drugs.

To elucidate the possible target-ligand binding selectivity, the binding properties (binding interactions, binding orientation and binding energy) of a database of combinatorially designed molecular hybrid scaffolds were studied using virtual screening approaches. Among the all the designs the hybrid pharmacophore designs (HPDs) six molecular scaffolds were identified as potential in silico “hits” for selective binding to the 5-LO target (Figure 1). Analysis of 5-LO target binding interactions of these HPDs within the ligand binding do-main (LBD) revealed characteristic hydrogen bond that was existing between all the designs and the key active binding site residue Phe 177. Our results support a model revealed that the binding interaction with corking amino acid (Gilbert NC, 2012) Phe 177 is the key inter-action responsible for accessing the U shaped site region for ligand binding in which the “cork” that shields the active site in the ab-sence of substrate serves as the active site portal, but the “corking” amino acid Phe-177 plays a critical role in positioning the sub-strate for catalysis (Mitra S, 2015). Phe-177 is required for active site entry or exit

Keywords:

5-lipoxygenase, leukotriene B4, atherosclerosis, hybrid molecular scaffolds, hybrid pharmacophore designs, virtual screening.

In summary, the “hits” identified have the potential to carry forward to experimental studies.

Figure 1: Figure illustrating the molecular scaffolds with hybrid pharmacophore designs (A-F) identified using virtual simulations for 5-LO inhibition.

References:

1. Verma S, Hussain ME. Obesity and diabetes: an update. *Diabetes & Metabolic Syndrome: Clinical Research & Reviews*. 2017 Jan 1;11(1):73-9.
2. Gilbert NC, Rui Z, Neau DB, Waight MT, Bartlett SG, Boeglin WE, Brash AR, Newcomer ME. Conversion of human 5-lipoxygenase to a 15-lipoxygenase by a point mutation to mimic phosphorylation at Serine-663. *The FASEB Journal*. 2012 Aug 1;26(8):3222-9.
3. Mitra S, Bartlett SG, Newcomer ME. Identification of the substrate access portal of 5-lipoxygenase. *Biochemistry*. 2015 Oct 8;54(41):6333-42.

Structure-Based Drug Design Studies Toward the discovery of Novel Chalcone Derivatives as a Potential Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) Inhibitors

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Abstract:

Human Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor-1 (EGFR), a transmembrane tyrosine kinase receptors (RTK), has been associated with several cancers, including breast, lung, ovarian, and anal cancers. Thus, the receptor was targeted by variety of therapeutic approaches for cancer treatments. A series of chalcone derivatives are among the most highly potent and selective inhibitors of EGFR described to date. A series of chalcone derivatives were proposed in this study to investigate the intermolecular interactions in the active site utilizing molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations. After careful analysis of docking results, compounds 1a and 1d were chosen for molecular dynamics simulation study. Extensive hydrogen bond analysis throughout 7 ns molecular dynamics simulation revealed the ability of compounds 1a and 1d to retain the essential interactions needed for the inhibition, especially MET 93. Finally, MM-GBSA calculations highlight on the capability of the ligands to bind strongly within the active site with binding energies of -44.04 and -56.6 Kcal/mol for compounds 1a and 1d, respectively. Compound 1d was shown to have near binding energy with TAK285 (-66.17 Kcal/mol), which indicates a high chance for compound 1d to exhibit inhibition activity, thus recommending to synthesis it to test its biological activity. It is anticipated that the findings reported here may provide very useful information for designing effective drugs for the therapeutic treatment of EGFR-related cancer disease.

Keywords:

EGFR; cancer; tyrosine kinase inhibitors; chalcone; molecular docking; molecular dynamics